

RE-DWELL Workshop 1 (Lisbon)

Deliverable 3.1

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RE-DWELL

Deliverable 3.1 RE-DWELL Workshop 1 (Lisbon)

Version 2

Authors:

Alexandra Paio (ISCTE – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa)

Leandro Madrazo (FUNITEC-La Salle URL)

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Executive summary

Three international workshops have been planned to take place in Lisbon (2021), Zagreb (2022) and Budapest (2023) as part of the RE-DWELL project. The first of these workshops, organized by the ISCTE – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa, has been carried out during the first year of the project activities in Lisbon, from September 22 to 24, 2021. This report focuses on the results of the first workshop in Lisbon.

The theme of three-day workshop was “Design, planning and building”, encompassing five sub-themes: Sustainable Planning; Industrialized Construction; Green Building; Building Retrofitting and Urban Regeneration; Housing Design Education. The programme was structured to fulfil various objectives: to follow-up the development of the ESRs’ research by fostering networking between the individual research projects, to conduct training activities related to ongoing structured courses (RMT1 and TS1), and to engage external stakeholders in the network actions (non-academic sectors, local administrations and civic organizations, dealing with sustainable and affordable housing). Each of two local partner organisations -CASAIS and Lisbon Municipality- were in charge of one session of the programme.

15 ESRs (one online), 10 supervisors/co-supervisors (7 in-person) and representatives of the two local partner organisations participated in the workshop. Some preparatory work was carried out by the ESRs (an abstract of their research projects, written and presented in an A1 poster). The posters were presented in a public exhibition at the Centro de Informação Urbana de Lisboa, where the sessions took place. The exhibition fomented a group discussion on the representation of a research project by means of a poster.

The workshop activities included lectures by representatives of the Lisbon Municipality, CASAIS engineers, external invited guests and professors from ISCTE-IUL specialized in the different subjects encompassed in the topic (participation, sustainability and housing policies), guided visits to the BIPZIP neighbourhoods and in a CASAIS building site. There were two sessions dedicated to the two ongoing courses: “Research, Methods and Tools 1” and “Transferrable Skills 1”. Flora Samuel moderated a public online roundtable with four guest researchers, which was followed by a discussion with ESRs, and Karim Hadjri and Krzysztof Nawratek gave lectures and organized group activities on transferable skills.

This work carried out in the Lisbon workshop was a step forward in understanding the significance of transdisciplinary approach when dealing with affordable and sustainable housing in Europe. The work reported in this document will inform the subsequent network activities. The report is also useful for faculty members from other institutions to learn about the work done in RE-DWELL.

1. Introduction

The first Lisbon Workshop on the theme “Design, planning and construction of affordable and sustainable housing” ran from September 22 to 24, 2021 in Lisbon at CIUL – Centro de Informação Urbana de Lisboa, a facility of Lisbon Municipality, with the collaboration of two local partners organizations - Lisbon Municipality and CASAIS Construction Company. This was the first in-person meeting of RE-DWELL consortium members, but still conditioned by Pandemic COVID-19 Portuguese and European measures, guidelines and recommendations of safety. Thus, all the sections were in hybrid mode (in-person and online).

The workshop theme “Design, planning and construction of affordable and sustainable housing” was addressed from multiple perspectives. The participants included invited guest speakers from professional practice, academia and local government, as well as other PhD students. The lectures were followed by group discussions and complemented by site visits. A roundtable to discuss transdisciplinary research for affordable and sustainable housing was open to the public via online.

The programme addresses five sub-themes which are part of the network’s training structure:

- **Sustainable Planning** – planning sustainable housing in urban areas; integration of sustainability dimensions (environmental, social and economic) and scales (building, district, city, region) in the design of affordable and sustainable housing;
- **Industrialized Construction** – design and construction of sustainable housing with industrialized methods; sustainable materials and building components; application of BIM and digital fabrication in affordable and sustainable housing;
- **Green Building** – methods and tools to support environment sustainability in design, planning and operation of residential buildings and urban environments; renewable resources at building and district level;
- **Building Retrofitting and Urban Regeneration** – adapting housing environments to dwellers’ needs; housing retrofitting; flexible and transformable housing layouts; applying ICTs to smart housing/living, post-occupancy evaluation;
- **Housing Design Education** – implementing in academic programmes inclusive housing design studios open to multiple stakeholders, embedded in local milieus.

Throughout the different programme activities, ESRs had the opportunity to demonstrate their ability to present and communicate research ideas and outputs to expert and non-expert audiences, to improve their understanding of transdisciplinary research methodologies and their application to their own projects, to develop personal qualities and self-management skills, and to engage with several external Portuguese stakeholders.

1.1. Contribution of local partners

ISCTE-IUL was in charge of the organization of the workshop. The collaboration of local organizations from the non-academic sectors - CASAIS and Lisbon Municipality - became key to accomplish the learning objectives and to strengthen the ties with local stakeholders (visit to CASAIS construction building, visit to BIPZIP Boavista Eco-neighbourhood and BIPZIP –

Marvila). The Lisbon Municipality gratefully provided the CIUL facilities for the event – with the support of Ana Marçal– as well as buses to the site visits– through Miguel Brito.

1.2. Participants

There were 45 participants, including ESRs, supervisors/co-supervisors, guest speakers and partners. All engaged and collaborated with one another and shared their knowledge of affordability and sustainability in housing from a transdisciplinary perspective. From RE-DWELL, 15 ESRs (one online), 10 supervisors/co-supervisors (7 onsite) and 2 partner organisations participated in the workshop (Figure 1):

- B1 FUNITEC (La Salle-URL), Spain, Project Coordinator (in-person)
- B2 Université Grenoble Alpes, France (in-person and online)
- B3 University of Sheffield, United Kingdom (in-person)
- B4 University of Zagreb, Croatia (online)
- B5 Hungarian Academy of Sciences Centre of Excellence, Hungary (in-person)
- B6 University of Cyprus, Cyprus (online)
- B7 Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain (in-person)
- B8 TU Delft, Netherlands (online)
- B9 ISCTE-Instituto Universitário de Lisboa, Portugal (in-person)
- B10 University of Reading, United Kingdom (online)
- PO1 Lisbon Municipality (in-person)
- PO7 CASAIS (in-person)

Figure 1. RE-DWELL participants in the Lisbon Workshop

1.3. RTM and TS training activities

The activities of two ongoing courses – RMT1 and TS1– were integrated in the workshop programme.

RTM1 “Session 4 : Transdisciplinarity research for affordable and sustainable housing” consisted of a roundtable with four guest researchers (outside RE-DWELL) on inter-, cross-or trans-disciplinary research on housing, including a reflection on the history of housing research (Figure 2). This session showcased examples of different approaches to housing issues aiming to transcend disciplines and/or to link research and practice. It was an online session that was accessible to the public. Afterwards, there was a debate restricted to RE-DWELL members in which ESRs asked the speakers questions.

TS1 “Session 5. Mini-lectures” consisted of three 30-minutes lectures (Figure 3): Lecture 1, on “Personal qualities and self-management”, by Karim Hadjri; Lecture 2, on “Ethics and data management”, by Krzysztof Nawratek, and Lecture 3, on “Open science and IPR”, by Krzysztof Nawratek (Open Science) and Karim Hadjri (IPR).

Figure 2. RMT1 course structure as integrated with the network activities.
 From: Adriana Diaconu (UGA), Research Methods and Tools 1 (RMT1)

Figure 3. TS1 course structure as integrated with the network activities.
 From: Karim Hadjri (USFD), Transferable Skills 1 (TS1)

1.4. Dissemination

There were dissemination activities before, and during the event, on different media, and with different purposes. The aim was to spread the Lisbon workshop results to a number of actors who would be potentially interested: researchers, local associations, professors, PhD students, policy makers and the general public. The implemented dissemination activities intended to offer a large number of supports: online, exhibitions, local journals, etc. The event was disseminated in local media and in the RE-DWELL social media channels (Figure 4) before and during the activities (Instagram, Twitter and Facebook) (Figure 5). A photographer from ISCTE-IUL made a reportage of the three-day programme¹. After the end of the workshop, ESRs published some reflections about their experiences in the RE-DWELL blog². The video of the roundtable is uploaded to the RE-DWELL YouTube channel³. These dissemination activities are also included in Deliverable 5.10 “Dissemination and Communication Outreach”.

During the workshop, there was a public exhibition of the posters created by ESRs to present their research project at CIUL - Centro de Informação Urbana de Lisboa (see Annex 3) (Figure 6). The exhibition enabled to have an open discussion about the ESRs projects and about the ways to represent them in a poster. In this discussion, ESRs voted the poster which most effectively conveyed the idea of the research project; a symbolic “prize” was awarded to the author of the selected posters, Leonardo Ricaurte (ESR15) (Figure 7).

Figure 4. Dissemination in the RE-DWELL website and in Jornal Económico

¹ Available at <https://www.flickr.com/photos/iscteiu/sets/72157719944468880/>

² Available at <https://www.re-dwell.eu/blog>

³ Available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sAQKjdVDo0>

Figure 5. Dissemination in Twitter and Instagram.

Figure 6. Public exhibition of posters of the ESR projects at CIUL - Centro de Informação Urbana de Lisboa

Figure 7. Award given to the author of the selected poster

2. Programme

The programme of the workshop was designed to fulfil various objectives: to follow-up the development of the ESRs' research by fostering networking between the individual research projects, conducting training activities related to ongoing structured courses (RMT1 and TS1), and engaging external stakeholders in the network actions (non-academic sectors, local administrations, civic organizations, dealing with sustainable and affordable housing). The two local partner organisations were in charge of organizing one session of the programme: CASAIS and Lisbon Municipality.

The programme (see Annex 1) was divided in two main blocks:

- morning sessions, with RE-DWELL learning training activities (Individual research projects networking; RMT1; and TS1);
- afternoon sessions, with guest speakers from professional practice, academia and local government, other PhD students, hands-on workshops and site visits.

Table 1. Programme of the workshop

Day	Timetable	Activities
FIRST DAY Wednesday, 22 September 2021	09:00 to 09:30	Welcome
	09:30 to 12:30	ESRs research projects
	12:30 to 14:00	Lunch break
	14:00 to 18:30	Lisbon Municipality session
	14:00 to 15:30	• Lectures
	15:30 to 16:30	• BIPZIP Hands-on workshop
	17:00 to 18:30	• Guided Tour BIPZIP neighbourhood
	20:00	Group dinner
SECOND DAY Thursday, 23 September, 2021	09:00 to 12:30	Roundtable
	12:30 to 14:00	Lunch break
	14:00 to 18:30	CASAIS session
	14:00 to 15:30	• Lectures
	15:30 to 17:00	• Hands-on workshop
	17:30 to 18:30	• Guided tour
	20:00	Group dinner
THIRD DAY Friday, 24 September, 2021	09:00 to 12:30	TS1: Lectures
	12:30 to 14:00	Lunch break
	14:00 to 17:30	ISCTE session
	14:00 to 15:30	• Lectures
	16:00 to 17:30	• Guided tour
	17:30	Welcome drink and group dinner

2.1. Activities

FIRST DAY

Wednesday, September 22th

Welcome

- Leandro Madrazo, RE-DWELL Project Coordinator
- Miguel Brito, Lisbon Municipality
- João Crispim, CASAIS
- Alexandra Paio, ISCTE / ISTAR-IUL

ESR research projects

Based on the updated abstracts of the ESR projects (research abstract posted on [RE-DWELL web page](#) and A1 poster summary) (see Annex 2 and Annex 3), the participants were asked to discuss the research projects in groups of three (two ESR and one supervisor/co-supervisor) and to draw a mind map (see Annex 4) answering these questions: What? Why? How? Who? (Figures 8, 9, 10).

The thirty-minute activity was followed by four-minute presentation by each group, which received the feedback from the participants (ESRs, supervisors, co-supervisors and secondment representatives) (Figure 11).

Figure 8. Individual Research Projects networking session

Figure 11. Individual Research Projects networking. Group presentation and discussion with ESRs, supervisors, co-supervisors and secondment representatives

Lisbon Municipality session

Facilitator: Dr. Alexandra Paio, ISCTE-IUL

The sub-theme that guided this session was “Sustainable Planning and Building “and “Retrofitting and Urban Regeneration” (Figure 12). The session was divided in lectures; hands-on workshop and site visit. Thirty-minute lectures each followed by questions and answers, and group activities.

Figure 12. Lisbon Municipality session

Lecture 1: Measuring citizen participation in urban regeneration. A reflection on the construction of the participation index for the BIP/ZIP programme in Lisbon, Roberto Falanga⁴, ICS (Figure 13).

The lecture provided an overview about the challenges of supporting robust evaluations of citizen participation in policymaking, by discussing the conceptualisation and operationalisation of the participation index for the BIP/ZIP programme.

Figure 13. Lisbon Municipality session – Lecture 1

Lecture 2: Lisbon metamorphosis, João Seixas⁵, NOVA FCSH (Figure 14).

Based on a book⁶ with the same name, the lecture provided an open, objective and descriptive, but above all analytical and interpretative reflection on the contemporary evolution of Lisbon. A city with a historical ballast, that today is a large metropolitan region, buzzing with life and interdependencies, at diverse scales.

⁴ Available at <https://www.ics.ulisboa.pt/en/pessoa/roberto-falanga>

⁵ Available at https://www.fcsh.unl.pt/en/college/teachers/jseixas_en/

⁶ Available at <https://amensagem.pt/2021/09/11/lisboa-em-metamorfose-feliz-estrategica-ou-solitaria-e-desigual/>

Figure 14. Lisbon Municipality session – Lecture 2

BIPZIP Hands-on workshop: Community-led local development, Miguel Brito⁷, Head of Housing and Local Development Lisbon Municipality Department (Figure 15).

Workshop to introduce Lisbon municipally BIPZIP strategy, which aimed to share the knowledge about the different tools to empower local communities⁸ in Lisbon.

Figure 15. Lisbon Municipality session – BIPZIP Hands-on Workshop

⁷ Available at <https://bipzip.lisboa.pt/index.htm>

⁸ Available at <https://cooperativitycity.org/2019/06/19/the-bip-zip-strategy-empowering-local-communities-in-priority-districts-of-lisbon/>

Guided Tour BIPZIP neighbourhood: Affordability and Social Cohesion, Alexandre Saraiva Dias, ORANGEarquitectura⁹ (Figures 16, 17)

The Boavista eco-neighbourhood visit (Figures 19, 20) aimed to obtain onsite knowledge of Lisbon/BIPZIP integrated model of sustainable innovation. This visit was guided by the architect that designed the building - Alexandre Saraiva Dias, the local taskforces GABIP¹⁰ coordinator – Sara Trindade - and the responsible of Boavista Neighbourhood Local Citizens Association - Bela Rebelo (Figure 18).

Figure 16. Lisbon Municipality session – Guided Tour BIPZIP neighbourhood

⁹ Available at <https://www.orangearquitectura.pt/>

¹⁰ Available at <https://cooperativecity.org/2019/06/19/the-bip-zip-strategy-empowering-local-communities-in-priority-districts-of-lisbon/>

Figure 17. Lisbon Municipality Session – Boavista Eco-Neighbourhood, Alexandre Saraiva Dias, ORANGEarquitectura

Figure 18. Lisbon Municipality session – Boavista Eco-Neighbourhood, Gabip-Sara Trindade And Boavista Neighbourhood Local Citizens Association - Bela Rebelo

Figure 19. Lisbon Municipality session – Boavista Eco-neighbourhood

Figure 20. Lisbon Municipality session – Boavista Eco-neighbourhood

SECOND DAY

Thursday, September 23th

RMT1 Research Methodologies and Tools

Training activities: Transdisciplinarity Research for Affordable and Sustainable Housing, organized by Dr. Adriana Diaconu, University of Grenoble. Public Roundtable, open debate with guest researchers, moderated by Prof. Flora Samuel, University of Reading (Figure 21).

The guest speakers were:

- **David Clapham**¹¹, Professor of Housing and Urban Studies, University of Glasgow
Housing and social theory, and housing policy.
- **Gilles Debizet**¹², Professor in Urban Planning, University Grenoble Alpes
Climate and energy transition, Territorialized learning and diffusion of expertise, Implementation of local climate policies and Environmental management of projects.
- **Doina Petrescu**¹³, Professor of Architecture and Design Activism, University of Sheffield,
Gender and Space, Participation in Architecture and Co-production and Urban Resilience
- **Ashraf Salama**¹⁴, Professor of Architecture, University of Strathclyde Design studio teaching practices, sustainable architectural and urban design, socio-cultural factors in shaping the built environment.

Figure 21. RE-DWELL Roundtable “Transdisciplinary Research for Affordable and Sustainable Housing”

This session was followed by questions and answers (Figure 22).

¹¹ Available at <https://housingevidence.ac.uk/author/david-clapham/> and <https://housingevidence.ac.uk/david-clapham-the-role-of-housing-academics/>

¹² Available at <https://www.pacte-grenoble.fr/membres/gilles-debizet>

¹³ Available at <https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/architecture/people/academic-staff/doina-petrescu> and <https://www.urbantactics.org/>

¹⁴ Available at <https://www.strath.ac.uk/staff/salamaashrafprof/>

Figure 22. RMT1 - Research Methods and Tools. Public roundtable

CASAIS session

Facilitator: Dr. Vasco Moreira Rato, ISCTE-IUL (Figure 23).

The sub-theme that guided this session was “Sustainable Planning and Building “and “Retrofitting and Urban Regeneration”. The session was divided in lectures; hands-on workshop and site visit. Thirty-minute lectures each followed by questions and answers, and group activities.

Figure 23. CASAIS session

Lecture 3: Industry construction digital transformation, Miguel Zenha¹⁵, Minho University (Figure 24).

The lecture provided an overview on industry construction digital transformation based on BIM opportunities for improve practice both for Architecture Engineering and Construction (AEC) professionals and clients.

Lecture 4: Circular economy and sustainability, João Wengorovius Meneses¹⁶, BCSD Portugal (Figure 25).

The lecture provided an overview on circular economy and sustainability challenges to the industry. We are racing against time to find lasting solutions that guarantee resources for future generations. The phrase "You may delay, but time will not" from Benjamin Franklin and "The Story of Stuff"¹⁷ from Annie Leonard were at the basis of this discussion.

Figure 24. CASAIS session - Lecture 3

¹⁵ Available at <http://civil.uminho.pt/mazenha/>

¹⁶ Available at <https://bcsdportugal.org/equipa/>

¹⁷ Available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9GorqroigqM>

Figure 25. CASAIS session - Lecture 4

CASAIS Hands-on workshop: BIM, Design and Digitalization Applied to Construction and Future buildings - Sustainable and Industrialized Construction, Miguel Pires and Pedro Lopes, Engineers in CASAIS¹⁸ Construction Company (Figure 26).

Workshop to introduce CASAIS digital transition strategy. With the increasing introduction of technology across industries, CASAIS is giving priority to the process of construction digitisation, with a focus on the use of technology to improve performance and the management chain.

Figure 26. CASAIS session. Hands-on Workshop

Guided tour CASAIS building site, Miguel Pires, CASAIS (Figures 27, 28)

¹⁸ Available at <https://www.casais.pt/en/3-business/1-engineering-and-construction/>

The DUO Building Collective Residential Housing, still in construction, visit aimed to obtain onsite knowledge of CASAIS process of construction digitisation (Figure 29).

Figure 27. CASAIS session - Visit to a construction site

Figure 28. CASAIS session - Visit to a construction site

Figure 29. CASAIS session – Explanation of the use of BIM in the construction

THIRD DAY

Friday, September 24th

TS1 Transferable Skills

Training activities: Personal qualities and self-management; Ethics and data management; Open science and IPR, organized by Dr. Karim Hadjri and Krzysztof Nawratek, University of Sheffield

Mini-lectures of thirty minutes each, followed by questions and answers and group activities (Figure 30), on the following topics:

- Personal qualities and self-management.
- Ethics and data management.
- Open science and IPR.

Figure 30. Transferable Skills session

ISCTE-IUL session

Facilitator: Dr. Paulo Tormenta Pinto, Head of Architecture and Urbanism Department, ISCTE-IUL (Figure 31).

Figure 31. ISCTE-IUL session

The theme of the session was “Housing Design Education”. It consisted of lectures; a hands-on workshop and a site visit. The thirty-minute lectures were each followed by a question and answer session.

Lecture 5: Public housing policies in Portugal, 1918-2018: A brief retrospect, Ricardo Agarez¹⁹, DINAMIA'CET, ISCTE -IUL (Figure 32).

The lecture provided an overview of “100 Years of Public Policies in Portugal”, in two ways: (1) at the level of the urban project and (2) in its relationship with the architectural project. Contributions to a morphological and typological study of the public housing landscape.

Lecture 6: Housing, challenges of urban interventions on self-produced places and search for spatial justice, Joana Pestana Lages²⁰, DINAMIA'CET, ISCTE -IUL (Figure 33).

The lecture focused on the challenges of urban interventions on self-produced places in the search for spatial justice. These practices promote a collective intelligence based on experiments in local urban contexts to create places for collaboration, sharing and collective ownership, often under the banner of ‘urban commons’.

Figure 32. ISCTE-IUL session - Lecture 5

Figure 33. ISCTE-IUL session - Lecture 6

¹⁹ Available at <https://www.dinamiacet.iscte-iul.pt/research-team/Ricardo-Costa-Agarez>

²⁰ Available at <https://www.dinamiacet.iscte-iul.pt/research-team/Joana-Pestana-Lages>

Guided tour: Housing in Marvila. From self-built to Social Housing innovation, Ana Catarino, ateliermob²¹ (Figures 34, 35).

The walking tour in the Marvila neighbourhood enabled participants to get an onsite knowledge of different periods of social housing public policies in Portugal (housing master plans, resettlements, from self-built to social housing). This visit was guided by anthropologist Ana Catarino, with the support of Ricardo Agarez and Joana Pestana Lages (Figure 36).

Figure 34. ISCTE-IUL session - Guided Tour in Marvila

Figure 35. ISCTE-IUL session - Guided Tour in Marvila

²¹ Available at <https://www.ateliermob.com/33>

Figure 36. ISCTE-IUL session - Guided Tour in Marvila

The workshop finished with an informal meeting of ESRs, supervisors and co-supervisors (Figure 37).

Figure 37. Meeting of supervisors, co-supervisors and ESRs

2.2. Evaluation

The workshop was evaluated by all the participants (in-person and online), through an anonymous online questionnaire (see Annex 7). The main goal of the questionnaire was to evaluate their experience and to detect any elements that could be improved in future workshops and summer schools.

The online questionnaire was answered by 13 ESRs and 4 supervisors/ co-supervisors, resulting in a response rate of 63%.

Participants were asked to express about the following aspects:

1. How would you rate the organization of the workshop? (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)
2. How would you evaluate the online sessions? (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)
3. Please evaluate the ESR's Research Projects session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)
4. Briefly explain the reasons for your ESRs Research Projects session evaluation
5. Please evaluate Lisbon Municipality session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)
6. Briefly explain the reasons for your Lisbon Municipality session evaluation
7. Please evaluate Roundtable session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)
8. Briefly explain the reasons for your Roundtable session evaluation
9. Please evaluate CASAIS session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)
10. Briefly explain the reasons for your CASAIS session evaluation
11. Please evaluate Transferrable Skills session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)
12. Briefly explain the reasons for your Transferrable Skills session evaluation
13. Please evaluate ISCTE-IUL session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)
14. Briefly explain the reasons for your ISCTE_IUL session evaluation
15. Any other comments or suggestions for upcoming network activities (workshops, summer schools)

In the first part of the survey participants were asked to assign a rating a general view. In the second part, they had to identify what they particularly liked and what could have been done better. At the end of the survey, they could add comments and recommendations for upcoming network activities. All the sessions were generally well appreciated (see Table 1).

Table 1. Lisbon Workshop: online evaluation

Questions	Answers	Supervisors/Co-supervisors	ESRs	Average
How would you rate the organization of the workshop? (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	17	4,80	3,80	4,15
How would you evaluate the online sessions? (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	17	4.40	3,75	4,08
Please evaluate ESRs Research Projects session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	16	4,75	4	4,38
Please evaluate Lisbon Municipality session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	16	4,50	4	4,25
Please evaluate Roundtable session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	17	4,60	3,92	4,26
Please evaluate CASAIS session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	16	4,5	3,17	3,84
Please evaluate Transferrable Skills session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	15	4,33	4,25	4,29
Please evaluate ISCTE-IUL session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	16	4,50	4,17	4,34

91% of ESRs answered positively to the Research Projects session:

“It was a good opportunity to discuss our project and understand others' projects. In addition, find interesting links to collaborate based on it in the near future”;

“It was an excellent opportunity to understand the actual projects of the other ESR's and engage in knowledgeable discussions. I have learned that despite the differences

and approaches (community, finance and design), collaboration is required later to reach the common goal of our projects”;

“It was a very meaningful and engaging exercise for the ESRs to identify connections not only within the working pairs but mainly through the discussion initiated by the presentations. Some very interesting points were brought up contributing also to our vocabulary development such as the discussion on empowerment and top-down/bottom-up notions”;

“Being divided into groups of two helped to find cross overarching themes and cross-cutting concepts, and the presentations sparked some interesting discussions”.

However, some ESR mentioned that:

“Useful to link together ESRs but seemed rather forced;

“Maybe breakout rooms where 3-4 people present cognate projects and discuss them in small groups would be more useful for individual feedback”;

“However, since I was participating remotely, sometimes was difficult to engage with the discussion”.

Regarding the ISCTE-IUL session, all ESR rated positively the activities. Some comments:

“It was in general very interesting to hear from the municipality. The onsite visit was also a valuable way to see what the presentations were all about”.

“Locally relevant knowledge was inspiring”

“It was very successful in introducing and immersing audience to particularities of challenges the municipality is facing”.

“(…) The site visit at Boavista neighbourhood was enlightening in the sense that we had different and contrasting inputs between the GAPBIP representative, the architect and the residents”.

Yet, some ESR mentioned that:

“The variety was excellent, but it was too condensed. I wish the sessions were shorter”;

“The content was a bit superficial. When we were getting to something interesting we were already late for the next presentation. I don't doubt the speakers were good and had interesting things to say but fewer presentations with more depth would have been better, maybe academic articles and suggested reading to go with it, context and background, would have produced more engagement”;

“I would have been good to learn more about the areas of failure and lessons learnt from the BIPZIP project, as there were more varied opinions from residents which hadn't been discussed”.

“(…) there was unfortunately not enough time for discussion and questions that many of us had and to my personal view would offer highly productive moments of reflections. Finally, it would have been great if there had been some gender balance in the panel, especially since the overall BIP/ZIP program was inspired and proposed by a woman and also counts a great number of female actors”.

Regarding the Roundtable session, it was positively rated by all ESRs. These comments exemplify the general view:

“The content was of high quality and I think it brought some of the most interesting discussions of the workshop. The hybrid setup was effective for what it was (though of course in person would have been even better)”;

“Well organised, pertinent speakers, good background readings”.

“Fascinating topics, helped to better understand the concept of transdisciplinarity”.

Nevertheless, some ESRs mentioned that they did not have enough time to discuss with the guests, and the hybrid session was not ideal to debate.

“(…) It would have been good to have more time to ask questions and interact with the members of the panel”;

“All in all, I think the format was the right one and I expect to see more of this kind of events, even with longer debates”;

“The only thing that I would mention is that the speakers introduced new concepts which are very helpful for interdisciplinary research and most of us were not familiar with this vocabulary. This is why it would be useful to have dedicated more time to the speakers to have 30min presentations before the discussion so that the topics would be introduced more clear and holistically to us. I think more time was needed for such important and concentrated topics”.

83% of ESRs answered positively to CASAIS session. These comments exemplify the general view

“well managed and very insightful given the varying points of view of participants' contributions”;

“Good energy for the extensive last day of site visits, very good choice of the site location”.

Some ESRs mentioned that:

“It was probably interesting for some of the ESRs but the presentation were way too long and technical... Considering most people could not relate to what it was all about. (...)”

“The presentations were too long and very superficial. The site visit was not interesting for all ESRs”.

The Transferrable Skills session only received positive feedback.

“Relevant to see what Re-dwell can do for us, interesting to hear about the book”.

“Very informative and engaging session that stretched the limits of the course and inspired knowledge-sharing among ESRs experiences outside the course”.

“Very interesting topics and important for our research, as always at the TR sessions”.

ESR mentioned:

“Great work, hope to see more practical being matters being addressed: how to divulge our own research for example, opportunities for fora to discuss our work. You know let's get re-dwell to the New European Bauhaus or the Venice Biennale”.

“Personally, I find the 30min talks a bit limited. I feel that I would like to have more in-depth talks but it could be that this is my personal perspective”.

The ISCTE-IUL session only received positive feedback, especially about the two guests speakers presentations. The guided tour to Marvila neighbourhood was considered important for some ESRs research projects.

“It was overall very interesting. The presentations were varied and the speakers touched very important topics”;

“Great presentations followed by a very nice tour in Marvila where we had the opportunity to engage with the presenters and follow the discussion. Overall, the experience was full, moving from the theoretical background, discussing pragmatism challenges and difficulties to a visualisation of the reality”;

“It was a good contribution to the general picture of Portugal's housing situation. I enjoyed the presentation about public housing policies in Portugal”.

“A very important day with useful information. The level of the presentations was exactly what I would expect from the workshop. Two amazing speakers, researchers with many years of experience in the area of housing studies, applying transdisciplinary perspectives, and with a very rich and thorough speech. I hope we will keep in contact with Ricardo, Joana, and ateliermob”.

Some ESRs mentioned that they would like to have more time for questions and discussions at the end of the lectures.

Regarding other comments or suggestions for upcoming onsite RE-DWELL network activities, some ESRs argued that they need more time for each session because was not enough time for

discussions. They would like to have more free time to visit the city.

About the issues related to the lack of coffee break and lunch break. There was no possibility to have meals or drinks in CIUL premises because of the pandemic COVID- 19 safety measures and rules. The place was chosen because is in centre of the city and has plenty of cafes and places for lunch around.

3. Conclusions

This work carried out in the Lisbon workshop represented a first step to understand the significance that a transdisciplinary approach has towards affordable and sustainable housing in Europe. The structure adopted encompassed the multiple components involved in a contemporary research engaging external stakeholders in the ITN actions (non-academic sectors, local administrations, civic organizations). The experience gained in the first onsite workshop will inform the next events of the network.

Annex 1 – ESR Research Projects

<div data-bbox="204 318 507 907"> <p>Annette Davis ESR1</p> <p>Host university DT - School of Architecture La Talle, Nanopool University</p> <p>Supervising team Leonán Martínez (Supervisor) Graciela Galván (Co-Supervisor) Alexandra Espin (Co-Supervisor)</p> </div>
<div data-bbox="209 1003 448 1059"> <p>September 17, 2021</p> </div>
<p>A framework for sustainable development of housing using Industrialized Construction</p> <p>Industrialized Construction (IC) is a broad term which encompasses systematic and controlled production. IC is no longer synonymous with mass production and prefabrication, and novel methods are more often taking place on site. Today IC is used to deliver customer orientated housing through mass customization and is increasingly used in combination with ICTs such as BIM to implement lean methods. IC raises the question of what constitutes a ‘home’; arguably some of the innovative methods intended for other purposes such as travel, military use, or product design, which have been adapted to housing are inherently unsuitable.</p> <p>There is growing attention on utilising IC to provide innovative solutions for today’s housing challenges in sustainability and affordability, in addition to managing building complexity and coordination with various fields. Recent ambitious EU targets to deliver Net Zero Energy Buildings and to incorporate Circular Economy have put increasing pressure on the construction industry to shift from the current paradigm to a more sustainable one. When used in conjunction with economies of scale IC can improve build quality, minimise waste, and reduce cost and time of construction. However, there needs to be a greater understanding of IC by both technical and non-technical stakeholders for its benefits to be fully realised.</p> <p>This project will investigate the benefits that a combination of industrialized methods and ICTs can provide in delivering sustainable and affordable housing. The research will seek to establish current methods suitable for housing within a framework, demonstrating the</p>

benefits in terms of sustainable development supported with case studies in collaboration with construction company Grupo Casais. Using a systems approach, the methodology will include establishing indicators in conjunction with Life Cycle Analysis (LCA). The analysis will cover all building stages, including beyond the end-of life-stage for a circular approach in line with the Level(s) framework. The proposed outputs will include a framework and guidelines for actors involved in the delivery of housing.

Saskia Furman
ESR

Host university
EPFL – School of Architecture Lausanne, Harvard
MIT University

Supervising team
Leandro Medeiros (Supervisor)
Karin Holm (Co-Supervisor)
Flora Sarrasin (Co-Supervisor)

September 17, 2021

Adapting European Social Housing to meet the Socio-Economic needs of Today’s Dwellers, and the Environmental needs of the Planet: A Framework for Renovation

Despite the disparity between their meanings the term social housing is often used synonymously with affordable housing. The project will discuss the upgrading of existing social housing stock – initially built as state-provided housing for different groups – to affordable (still a contested term) and sustainable housing, in accordance with the current Sustainable Development Goals (SDG’s)

When renovating existing social housing we must address the socio-economic characteristics of today’s dwellers, the surrounding infrastructure, and energy efficiency standards.

The objective of this research is to develop a matrix encompassing the multiple dimensions and issues to consider in a mid- to large-scale renovation programme. Organised under broad categories, including urbanity, sustainability, social, connectivity and more, the framework will identify key issues to be improved, such as the building envelope, internal layout, social mix, safety, and energy efficiency. I will then analyse the set of criteria against a number of case studies to assess the successes of existing social housing stock and areas to be improved. The chosen case studies will be post-war European social housing that has been partly renovated since construction. Consultations with INCASÒL will help determine an optimal set of criteria, as well as provide a rich data set for further analysis during my secondment.

The following questions will be addressed during case study analysis: How long should evaluation of each case study take place? What problems were identified by renovations and how were solutions found? What did the renovators want to achieve? How do the renovations align with the SDG’s?

From the results of the matrix I will originate a comprehensive multi-criteria framework that suggests what renovations should occur, why they should occur, and identify the multiple actors and stakeholders that will benefit.

Christophe Verrier

ESR3

His university:

UR - Poitiers - Laboratoire de Sciences Sociales,
Université Grenoble Alpes

Supervising team:

Maïté Dourson (Supervisor)
Justine Baccou (Co-Supervisor)
Hélène Mouton (Co-Supervisor)

September 17, 2021

Housing governance beyond city boundaries : a multi-level analysis of policy path dependencies in European cities.

Across Europe, cities are often at the uncomfortable crossroad between the dismantlement of post-war national housing policies, pressing housing needs, and an imperative to engage in entrepreneurial policies to compete on the global scale. Yet, at the same time, localities are fertile grounds for housing innovation, whether stemming from public authorities or bottom-up initiatives. This paradoxical position raises the question: to what extent can localities shape specific housing outcomes in divergence from nationally steered policies and pressures from a globalized Neoliberal economic system?

Large urban development projects embody this paradox – entrepreneurial policy instruments, restricted (more or less) by housing and planning regulation, led by complex governing entities which are given varied and often contradicting goals. This project will investigate whether these developments can be steered by local regimes to yield affordable and sustainable housing responding to the needs of local communities.

Finding its theoretical grounding in works on institutional regimes within housing research and on urban entrepreneurialism from urban studies, this research aims to bridge a gap between an over-reliance on the national scale in the former and a difficulty accounting for variation in the latter. Building on the concept of local housing regime, the research aims to map the enabling and disabling forces that stakeholders can mobilize over time to steer the construction of dwellings in directions responding to local specificities.

The research will assess the outcomes of urban development projects at different points in time through their tenure structure, design and implementation processes and the socio-economic profile of their inhabitants. Ultimately, by engaging in a comparison between different European cities, this research should offer a better understanding of the forces shaping housing outcomes in urban development projects.

Aya Elghandour
ESR4

Host university
03 – Sheffield School of Architecture (SSA),
University of Sheffield

Supervising team
Kate Hogg (Supervisor)
Aspoutof Iorakian (Co-Supervisor)
Yousa Moini Razi (Co-Supervisor)

September 17, 2021

Life Cycle Economic and Social Cost-based Design

Housing affordability and housing quality are two key facets that influence social housing provision. The first is concerned with the overall cost of having and maintaining a house without adding unwanted financial pressure which may lead to psychological burdens on households. On the other hand, housing quality is pertinent to providing a pleasant, healthy, durable, and safe indoor and outdoor built environment, which in return rises housing costs. In this respect to measure housing affordability, Life Cycle Cost Analysis (LCCA) can be used as an economic analysis method to estimate the overall cost of building alternatives starting from the design, construction, operation, till its disposal phase. Therefore, housing alternatives with the lowest overall cost, and in line with quality, can be identified from early design stages where the most influential building decisions are made.

While LCCA is crucial in selecting the optimum housing alternative, it, however, increases the design complexity. For instance, estimating energy consumption, which occupies the largest portion of buildings' LCC, involves the use of various computational tools and requires reliable data that might not be available. In addition, from a social perspective, assessing housing quality and its LCC based on post-occupancy social feedback, is still limited. Accordingly, there is a real need to transform occupants' feedback and their potential role in energy saving into useful data to support design teams. In practice, Building Information Modelling (BIM) allows storing and managing all building data in a single platform. Thus, it has the potential of conducting LCCA and accessing real-time data from completed buildings. However, there is a present lag in providing an applicable feedback loop to inform design teams with this reliable data. Moreover, there is a dearth of research that integrates LCCA and social dimensions into BIM.

Therefore, this PhD aims to develop a market-friendly framework that achieves this integration to reduce the total LCC and inform the design based on occupants' real needs.

The study will adopt a mixed approach of quantitative and qualitative research methods. A taxonomy of literature will be conducted to explore LCCA and social assessment methodologies, parameters, and optimization goals that are adequate for BIM to inform the design of the framework. This framework will be developed following four phases of fieldwork consisting of surveys, interviews, a co-design event with stakeholders and residents, as well as simulation-based comparative analysis of real social housing case studies. As a result, the study will be able to classify and prioritize the most efficient data to be utilized for BIM models. Finally, the framework applicability will be tested for a social housing unit. Therefore, the study is expected to enable informed economic and social-based decision-making from early design stages using BIM to promote housing sustainability and improve affordability.

Mahmoud Alsaeed

ESR5

Host university

BSA - Sheffield School of Architecture (SSA), University of Sheffield

Supervising team

Marie Hejar (Supervisor)
 Krzysztof Pawlinski (Co-Supervisor)
 Ignacio Galan (Co-Supervisor)

September 17, 2021

Environmental Sustainability of Future Social Housing

Environmental sustainability and resource efficiency are vital concepts to improve and protect our planet. Both concepts are also relevant to housing design, construction and use. With the support of local housing communities, the UK social housing sector is set to increase rapidly. In the UK, housing accounts for 30 per cent of the total energy use, 27 per cent of UK carbon dioxide emissions, while at the same time, social housing forms up to 18 per cent of total housing stock. Therefore, we must reconsider new ways of building sustainable and affordable homes that improve the quality of the built environment and create better places for people to live.

This project addresses two challenges. On the one hand, it establishes a clearer conceptual understanding of low-cost sustainable housing by investigating the definitions, principles, and theories associated with its construction. On the other hand, it examines sustainability practices currently in use by looking at the sustainability tools, guidelines, codes, and standards for achieving low-carbon homes. Consequently, this project will answer the following questions in the UK context: how do we define and measure housing sustainability? What tools can be used to achieve low-carbon housing? How do we achieve a decarbonized housing sector?

A mixed methods research design will be used. Qualitative instruments, including a literature review and case studies analysis, will identify current sustainability definitions, meanings and methods of practice. Meanwhile, quantitative instruments focused on statistical reports and sustainability codes aim to review the existing assessment methods and develop a comprehensive understanding of sustainability assessment principles.

The planned outcome of this project is to develop a comprehensive framework that promotes the sustainability of social housing. This framework will be developed in collaboration with relevant stakeholders, including local social housing communities. It will

include a theoretical database that defines the theories and principles of “low-carbon design and planning of housing”; at the same, it will form a clear, practical guideline for achieving “decarbonized housing” by improving current standards and codes of practice, therefore bridging the gap between theories of housing sustainability and actual practices of housing construction in the UK.

<p>Marko Horvat ESRG</p> <p>Host university D4 - Institute for Social Policy-ISP, University of Zagreb</p> <p>Supervising team Gábor Bozsonyi (Supervisor) Ivan Hrnac (Co-Supervisor) Bernd von Sotter (Co-Supervisor)</p>	<p>September 17, 2021</p>
<p>Comparative analysis of social housing policies' modernization impacts in selected post-socialist countries</p> <p>With more than 60% of the population residing in cities, the world is dealing with unprecedented pressure on resources and infrastructure. Housing markets are unstable, supply chains fragile, and the trend of increasing wage gap presents an urgent need for coherent and future-proof social policy in many areas of the welfare state.</p> <p>In Europe, many eastern countries went through transition from socialism to capitalism in the early 1990s. For most of them, a “give-away” privatisation of public housing stock took place, practicing a mass sell-off of public housing stock to sitting tenants. That led to unequal wealth distribution at the beginning of the capitalist market system and erased the social housing systems from the political map.</p> <p>Over the course of three years, this research will look into Slovenian, Croatian and Slovakian social housing policy development since the transition period and the path-dependency that originated in the old regime. Evidence will be gathered to produce solid policy recommendations based on local knowledge and context, collaborating with a cross-European community of experts and academics.</p> <p>A literature review will be conducted to produce a deep understanding of social housing theory and the role of the government in the current housing system and the ability of this system to provide affordable and sustainable housing. This will provide fundamental knowledge for a comparative analysis of how changes in social housing policies affected the social housing regime in Slovenia, Croatia and Slovakia. Moreover, good practice examples of housing provisions for vulnerable groups across Europe will be identified,</p>	

having in focus the potential for transferability and scalability of solutions in selected countries.

Transdisciplinarity of the research will consider other ESRs' work and will work together with academic and non-academic stakeholders to understand the most important issues in developing and implementing social housing policies in these countries, focusing on the ability of different housing regimes to deliver affordable homes for vulnerable groups.

<p>Anna Martin ESR7</p> <p>Host university IS - Institute for Sociology, Centre for Social Sciences, Hungarian Academy of Sciences Centre of Excellence</p> <p>Supervising team Anikó Csizmady (Supervisor) Anita Dóczi (Co-Supervisor) Géza von Borzsei (Co-Supervisor)</p>
<p>September 17, 2021</p>
<p>Comparative analysis of social housing policies' modernization impacts in selected post-socialist countries</p> <p>In 2021 the European Parliament finally responded to the housing crises, calling member states of the union to recognise adequate housing as a fundamental human right. The purpose of this research is to investigate the origins of the housing crisis and its implications in Central and Eastern Europe, how intensified disparities evolved over time.</p> <p>This research aims to understand the reasons why affordable housing has become both a social and economic problem (considering path dependent processes). Unaffordable, and inadequate housing leads to inequalities and these inequalities can cause significant differences in lifetime earnings. The goal is the understand the main causal (often reinforcing) mechanisms and conflicting paradigms that formulated the current housing situation.</p> <p>Unlike in western Member States, where social welfare systems are well developed, and the public housing system is quite mature, eastern member states still have a weak social welfare system. Many people of these countries from the low- and middle-income classes cannot afford their own houses, and there's no realistic scenario for them to be able to have future savings and change the situation.</p> <p>The research would employ a mixed research design to reach its objective and will follow a linear process, starting with a systemic literature review and context familiarisation, followed by data collection and data analysis. Results of the research will enable the researcher to have an intelligent estimate of the forces that caused the housing crises and provide the reader with theoretically informed and empirically verified knowledge about 'best practices' of adequate housing.</p>

The uniqueness of the research is that it would consider the economic, social, environmental and governance challenges of housing affordability at the same time.

<p>Andreas Panagidis ESRE</p> <p>Host university DE Department of Architecture, University of Cyprus</p> <p>Supervising team Nafis Othmanides (Scientist) Andreas Savvides (Co-Supervisor) Gabor Csizsik (Co-Supervisor)</p>
<p>September 17, 2021</p>
<p>Urban Living Labs and the Role of Users in the Co-Creation of Sustainable Housing: Housing as Community Infrastructure</p> <p>The priorities of contemporary urban-environmental policy are increasingly being criticised for not producing equitable inhabitations as an underlying pro-business agenda has been found in tension especially with the social goals of sustainability and leading to negative interrelated socio-environmental consequences. Moreover, the tried techno-managerial approaches to sustainable urban development are being criticised for failing in the governance of urban spaces and disempowering citizens as the access to affordable housing and sustainable neighbourhoods is becoming increasingly inequitable. In the face of mounting risks from climate change, systemic transformations at many different levels are not only becoming increasingly urgent, they are perhaps imperative for re-defining sustainable development and addressing these contemporary urban challenges.</p> <p>One approach that addresses the complexity of such urban problems recognises that sustainability and affordability of housing should be addressed simultaneously, responding to the interests of communities. Collaborative forms of governance and collectively managed socio-spatial resources discussed in research on the urban commons, are emerging paradigms of alternative practices influencing contemporary housing discourses. More recently, the importance of a place-based approach to innovation and urban experimentation highlights the role of the local context in sustainability transitions and social innovation literature. This research will investigate practices in housing design by looking at the surrounding socio-ecological contexts, place-making processes and other aspects that ‘localise’ housing.</p> <p>It is also still largely unstudied how social dimensions of sustainable development, for example social cohesion, and sense of place can contribute to housing research at the intersection of the home and its supporting urban systems. This is especially important in</p>

the design of affordable housing environments which should afford lower-income residents connections to community resources and broader sets of opportunities. The Urban Living Lab approach will be used in the co-production of collaborative knowledge, involving interactions between the local community and public authorities to form strategies for place-based action in residential environments that support housing and may lead to housing as a form of infrastructure embedded in community-driven social, economic and ecological processes.

<p>Effrosyni Roussou ESR9</p> <p>Host university DE - Department of Architecture, University of Cyprus</p> <p>Supervising team Nida Charalambous (Supervisor) Cata Soriano (Co-Supervisor)</p>
<p>September 17, 2021</p>
<p>Urban Living Labs and the Role of Users in the Co-Creation of Sustainable Housing: From creator to enabler: exploring the potential of co.design.build courses in contemporary architectural education</p> <p>Contemporary architectural education, especially in southern European contexts, remains widely ineffective in addressing the increasingly complex and ever-shifting realities that urban dwellers are called to face. While economic fluctuations, climate change and the various political agendas are spawning challenges that are profoundly transforming living environments and reshaping contemporary housing provision, architectural education remains widely unchanged. Persisting normative approaches result in the architect as a detached figure, operating top-down, in a purely theoretical plane and completely cut off from the socio-cultural aspects and implications as well as the end users of their work.</p> <p>Even though design-build courses, as part of architectural curricula around the world, have shown promising results in challenging the archetype of the architect as an omnipotent creator the current focus is -to a large extent- on the development of students' technical and managerial skills. This project aims to explore the opportunities for radical change within architecture schools, especially in the European south, through the implementation of critical, transdisciplinary, collaborative/multistakeholder co.design.build courses within a social and environmental sustainability framework and a focus on acupuncture interventions on the neighbourhood scale.</p> <p>The research approach that will be followed is community-based participatory action research (CBPAR), which will unfold in two stages: (1) co-creation of the course structure, aims, objectives and approach through workshops with faculty and prospective students, drawing from comparative analyses of relevant curricula on an international level and (2) course implementation and testing in two separate iterations (spring & autumn 2023). The second part will involve close monitoring of participants' (students, teachers, local</p>

stakeholders) views and perceptions on the course and their own involvement, before, during and after the completion of each iteration.

The expected outcome of this research is a set of strategies in creating and running a transdisciplinary, multistakeholder co.design.build course that “thinks globally but operates locally” as well as a thorough and reflexive evaluation of the experimentation process.

Zoe Tzika
ESR10

Host university
E3 – School of Architecture, Universitat Politècnica de València

Supervising team
Celia Sánchez (Supervisor)
Adrianna Chiriac (Co-Supervisor)
Ana Martínez (Co-Supervisor)

September, 17, 2021

Co-creation of sustainable living environments

The aim of the research is to critically investigate the sustainable retrofit of neighbourhoods and housing through collective and community-based practices. The research takes its departure from the need for a critical exploration of what defines a sustainable urban environment, that promotes socially inclusive, environmentally aware and affordable modes of living, that is co-produced by the local population, according to their needs. The research seeks to connect the act of inhabiting with the active involvement in shaping the built environment and creating sustainable communities with respect to their identity and socio-cultural characteristics.

Housing is becoming unaffordable for a big part of society, because of the rising real-estate values, financialization and deregulation of the housing market and a permanent and global housing crisis. At the same time, the right to affordable housing should not be separated from the right to decent housing and to access resources, infrastructures and services. Often, urban areas are being (re)developed following neoliberal urbanism and centralized decision-making, which leads to dislocation of the local populations, gentrification or exclusion. In addition, the climate crisis strengthens the importance of re-considering the dominant paradigm of urban development, suggesting more ecological approaches and energy efficiency. Bottom-up practices of collective retrofit and cohousing are creating alternatives that challenge the commodification and precarization of housing and the atomization and isolation of people, offering opportunities for collaboration, appropriation, self-management and empowerment of the residents.

The research will investigate collaborative practices of housing with the adaptive reuse and retrofit of existing built environments, understanding the socio-political context in which they emerge to create perspectives that go beyond a normative approach. I will use case study research with a mixed method of quantitative and qualitative data, to investigate the

process and the characteristics of retrofit cohousing. The post-occupancy evaluation will be followed by participatory action research. Also, the field surveys will be combined with interviews and ethnographic methodologies to develop a comprehensive analysis of the existing conditions. The aim is to arrive at analysis and methodologies for sustainable retrofit of existing buildings considering the social implications and exploring the potential of collaborative housing.

<p>Tijn Croon ESR11</p> <p>Host university iis - Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment (ABE), TU Delft</p> <p>Supervising team Mona Ganga (Supervisor) Adrienne Colman (Co-Supervisor) Joris Heester (Co-Supervisor)</p>	
<p>September 17, 2021</p>	
<p>The Governance of a Just Housing Transition: Targeting Disadvantaged Households within the European ‘Renovation Wave’</p> <p>As residential energy consumption constitutes a significant share of Europe’s carbon emissions, the European Commission aims to establish a ‘Renovation Wave’ by incentivising energy efficiency measures and renewable energy sources while discouraging the usage of fossil fuels. However, even though it is generally accepted that this can lower housing expenditure in the long term, policymakers are becoming increasingly concerned about the short-term negative effects that retrofit costs and levies may have on the position of disadvantaged households. This research seeks to provide insight into the effects of sustainability objectives on their ability to afford housing and explores the embeddedness of ‘just transition’ principles within multilevel housing governance. The overarching principles of recognitional justice, procedural justice and distributional justice will be conceptually deepened and empirically assessed in different housing contexts. To that end, I first intend to determine specific vulnerabilities that arise in this transition by quantitatively assessing microdata. The methodologies during this phase will include complex proportional assessment (COPRAS), a form of multicriteria decision making (MCDM), combined with more conventional regression techniques. Identifying the characteristics of those households at risk could help to comprehend differences and subsequently design policies that accommodate particular needs. In the following phase I will focus on case studies at different levels of housing governance, looking at the application of just transition principles on a national and supranational level, but also evaluating how municipalities, housing associations and other local actors identify inequitable transition outcomes and incorporate fairness within their policies. A mix of qualitative methods, such as interviews, focus groups and surveys, will be used to help understand the barriers vulnerable groups encounter and the special treatment this may require. Besides scientific publications, the project’s output will include a policy framework</p>	

with guidelines for housing governance actors to address vulnerabilities and deliver a just housing transition.

<p>Alex Fernandez</p> <p>ESR12</p> <p>Host university HD - Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment (ABE), TU Delft.</p> <p>Supervising team Merje Eelens (Supervisor) Marjolijn Halpern (Co-Supervisor) Geert Brouwer (Co-Supervisor)</p>
<p>September 17, 2021</p>
<p>Comparative Analysis of Affordable and Sustainable Housing Policies in Europe</p> <p>This project's main research goal is to identify and compare policies for the affordable retrofit of Europe's built environment. The analytical framework draws from various disciplines including economics, public policy, and complexity science. These disciplines provide the foundations to four research streams:</p> <p>Analysing of user costs and cash-flows implications for various housing retrofit policies within the Dutch national context. By comparing the economic implications of different policies across households and housing typologies, this line of inquiry seeks to identify the financial impacts over renters, owners, and landlords with varying income levels.</p> <p>Constructing an Agent-Based Model of the housing market. This model aims to capture the second and third-order effects that modifications to the housing stock can have over house prices and ultimately affordability. Here the focus will be on the potential distributional effects of housing retrofit.</p> <p>Adapting the preceding model to account for particularities across countries and urban areas. This model will include the economic and social contexts that condition policy outcomes across European housing systems.</p> <p>Exploring institutional and policy design across different public and private organisations. This mainly qualitative stream will critically analyse institutional arrangements that favour the adoption of affordable and sustainable housing policies. The point of contact with experts will be the RE-DWELL network, secondments, and case studies.</p> <p>These four research streams are empirically and methodologically led, however, ESR12 also aspires to contribute to the theoretical underpinning of public policy analysis, housing</p>

economics, and critical social sciences. These disciplines, while dealing with the same research topics, have evolved through divergent perspectives; ESR12 seeks to strengthen the links between them. By bringing these perspectives together, this project intends to formulate realistic policy recommendations for the design of a fair transition to a low-emissions' built environment.

Androniki Pappa

ESR13

Host university

TEI - School of Technology and Architecture,
University Institute of Lisbon (ISCTE)

Supervising team

Alexandre Pais (Supervisor)
Fátima Duarte (Co-Supervisor)
Cátia Serôdio (Co-Supervisor)

September 17, 2021

Citizen participation evaluation and urban co-governance: lessons from BIP/ZIP and the world of commons

In recent decades many governments across the globe have implemented participatory and commons-oriented policies in urban regeneration, contributing to the active engagement of citizens in planning at different scales, as well as in co-managing the urban commons.

Ranging from bottom-up good practices of participation that evolve into policies, to top-town initiatives that recognise the benefits of multi-stakeholder governance for local development, the repository of case studies demonstrate an array of experimental planning and governance tools. Among others, these include creative communities, social innovation initiatives, participatory funding, local policies, city regulations or protocols and networks of good practices. One such instrument of public policy is the ongoing BIP/ZIP local development strategy, constituted in 2010 by the Lisbon City Council. Focusing on priority intervention neighbourhoods and zones, BIP/ZIP enables bottom-up citizen participation in co-government models, urban interventions and cultural initiatives and counts to date 391 realised projects in Lisbon.

Despite the increasing experimentation on participatory policies and governance, several researchers identify the deficiency of an evaluation mechanism for their effectiveness as the greatest challenge and -possibly- need in order to highlight good practices and trajectories. The plurality in goals, methodologies and definitions of each case complicates the essay in developing replicable models of evaluation.

After ten years of implementation the BIP/ZIP strategy can become a lighthouse for knowledge-sharing for other cities. A comprehensive research on the program's collaborative, operational and funding tools, together with a taxonomy of participatory

governance projects internationally and a review on the published empirical evaluation literature is formative to identify indicators and key vocabulary for a transferable model of evaluation and co-governance. Therefore, the purpose of this project is to identify patterns and indicators and further experiment through community-based participatory research, in order to develop an evaluation toolkit integrated into a co-governance model.

The results of the research will contribute to the scientific discussion on participation evaluation, as well as to the design of a co-governance model. Starting with BIP/ZIP and Lisbon Municipality and communities, the model will offer itself as a tool for collaborative local development and co-management of the urban commons, contributing to a social-inclusive, sustainable future.

<p>Leonardo Ricaurte ESR15</p> <p>Host university RTS - School of Built Environment, University of Reading</p> <p>Supervising team Pinar Samat (Supervisor) Lorraine Farrelly (Co-Supervisor) Jean-Christophe Dassin (Co-Supervisor)</p>
<p>September 17, 2021</p>
<p>Housing regeneration in Europe: Possibilities for social value creation in the context of the Renovation Wave</p> <p>In the framework of integrated plans such as the Renovation Wave and the European Green Deal, several urban renewal projects are to be implemented in cities across the continent in the coming years. This depicts a remarkable opportunity to channel expertise, decision-making and funds towards better practices and trigger a paradigm shift in city-making. Accordingly, the research question that will steer the development of this study is: How can the social value and wellbeing generated by housing projects be better captured and capitalized in the context of major urban regeneration schemes?</p> <p>Housing projects that envision creating more cohesive and inclusive communities will be targeted in a series of data collection activities, planned to offer the possibility of experimenting with different methods, and considering all the actors involved. The methodology to be used is a mix of quantitative and qualitative data collection processes, incorporating methods like participatory action research, and selected from the array of existing Post-Occupancy Evaluation (POE) frameworks and social value toolkits for architecture, selected through a systematic literature review. The feedback acquired will be instrumental in informing the development of an own tailor-made social evaluating framework. The intention is to demonstrate the benefits of conducting POE and showcasing projects that reconcile affordability and sustainability. And ultimately inspire decision-makers, private developers, academia, and civil society to get on board.</p> <p>The secondments that complement this research are fundamental for the creation of tangible and productive links between academia and industry. In this aspect, the findings obtained will potentially contribute to the institutions' own activities. Counting on Clarion's expertise in regeneration projects for carrying out data collection activities. Consequently, England and France are subjects of a comprehensive analysis, yet other countries</p>

participants of the RE-DWELL network remain considered possible sources of input that resonates with the research aims. This study emphasizes the great potential that resides in incorporating practices such as POE, wellbeing and quality of life and social value assessment when developing housing regeneration schemes. Hence, by leveraging on the experiences and momentum, the generation of new projects could be attained.

Annex 2 – ESR Research Projects (posters)

Delivering affordable and sustainable housing in Europe

Design & construction of energy efficient housing using industrialized methods: A framework for sustainable development of housing using Industrialized Construction

ESR1: Annette Davis

Supervisor: Dr Leandro Barbato
Host University: School of Architecture La Salle, Ramon Llull University

Project description

Industrialized Construction (IC) is a broad term which encompasses systematic and controlled production. Today IC is used to deliver customer oriented housing and is increasingly used in combination with ICTs such as BIM in improvement from off-site. There is growing attention on utilizing IC to provide innovative solutions for today's housing challenges, however, there needs to be a greater understanding by both technical and non-technical stakeholders for its benefits to be fully realized. This project will investigate how the combination of industrialized methods and ICTs can deliver sustainably developed housing through a framework, supported with case studies in collaboration with construction company Grupo Casais.

Secondments

- ISCTE | Intern methods for the integration of BIM with IC
- UPV | Support in establishing LCA indicators and analysis methodology
- Casais | Expert industry knowledge and case study data

Theoretical & conceptual framework connections

Methodologies

The project seeks to measure the holistic benefits of IC in housing with indicators or 'inputs'. The output framework and guidelines are aimed at designers and policy makers to deliver improved housing for the end users or 'builders'. This will be achieved using a systems approach and establishing indicators for Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) for all building stages, tested with case studies.

 This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101019164

Adapting European Social Housing to meet the Socio-Economic needs of Today's Dwellers, and the Environmental needs of the Planet: A Framework for Renovation

ESR2: Sessia Furman

Supervisor: Dr. Leonardo Machado
Host University: School of Architecture La Salle, Ramon Llull University

Project Description:

Investigate the upgrading of existing social housing stock – initially built as state provided housing for different groups - to affordable with a corrected tenor and sustainable housing, in accordance with the current Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Address the socio-economic characteristics of today's dwellers, the surrounding infrastructure, and energy efficiency standards.

Case Research 2017

Matrix Methodology:

Organised under broad categories / indicators, the framework will identify key issues to be improved. I will then analyse the set of criteria against a number of case studies to assess the successes of existing social housing stock and areas to be improved.

Case Study queries:

- What should be the length of evaluation?
- What problems were identified by renovators?
- How were solutions found?
- What did the renovators want to achieve?
- How do the renovations align with the SDG's?

Case	Indicator	Exp. issues	Requirements met
1	1.1	1.1.1	1.1.1
2	2.1	2.1.1	2.1.1
3	3.1	3.1.1	3.1.1
4	4.1	4.1.1	4.1.1
5	5.1	5.1.1	5.1.1
6	6.1	6.1.1	6.1.1
7	7.1	7.1.1	7.1.1
8	8.1	8.1.1	8.1.1
9	9.1	9.1.1	9.1.1
10	10.1	10.1.1	10.1.1
11	11.1	11.1.1	11.1.1
12	12.1	12.1.1	12.1.1
13	13.1	13.1.1	13.1.1
14	14.1	14.1.1	14.1.1
15	15.1	15.1.1	15.1.1
16	16.1	16.1.1	16.1.1
17	17.1	17.1.1	17.1.1
18	18.1	18.1.1	18.1.1
19	19.1	19.1.1	19.1.1
20	20.1	20.1.1	20.1.1

Output - Multi-criteria Framework:

- WHAT? What renovations should occur?
- WHY? Why they should occur?
- WHO? Identify the multiple actors and stakeholders that will benefit.

Housing governance beyond city boundaries: a multi-level analysis of policy path dependencies in European cities.

ESR3: Christophe Verrier

Supervisor: Pauletti Duarte - Co-supervisors: Adriana Diaconu and Joris Hoekstra
 Host University: Laboratoire Paolié, Université Grenoble-Alpes

Background	Abstract
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="width: 45%;"> <p>Housing regimes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulties in accounting for paths of institutional development • Divergence in the national scale • Difficulties in identifying locally shaped housing regimes within regions </div> <div style="width: 45%;"> <p>Critical urban studies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobilisation and (re)activation of existing features of urban capitalities • Housing as a commodification • Expansion of environmental urban policies </div> </div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 10px;"> <p>Large Urban Development Projects</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locally shaped • Locally diversified • Locally pluralised </div>	<p>Across Europe, cities are often at the uncomfortable crossroads between the dismantlement of state-led national housing policies, increasing housing precarity, and the global imperative for entrepreneurial projects. Yet, at the same time, localities are fertile grounds for housing innovation, whether stemming from public authorities or bottom-up initiatives. This paradoxical position raises the question to what extent can localities shape specific housing outcomes in divergence from nationally steered policies and pressures from a neoliberal economic system?</p> <p>Large urban development projects embody this paradox – entrepreneurial policy instruments, restricted (often or less) by housing and planning regulations, set by national governing entities given central and often conflicting goals. This project will investigate whether these developments can be steered by local regimes in ways affordable and sustainable housing responding to the needs of local communities.</p> <p>Finding its theoretical grounding in works on institutional regimes in housing research and on Neoliberal entrepreneurialism within urban studies, this research aims to bridge a gap between an over-reliance on the national scale in the formal and a different accounting for variation at the urban. Building on the concept of local housing regimes, the research aims to map the enabling and disabling forces that stakeholders can mobilise over time to steer the construction of dwelling decisions responding to local specificities.</p> <p>The research will assess the outcomes of urban development projects at different points in time through their tenure structures, design and implementation processes and the socio-economic profile of their residents. Ultimately, by engaging in a comparative between different European cities, this research should offer a better understanding of the forces shaping housing outcomes in urban development projects beyond national policy and neoliberal economic imperatives.</p>
Objectives	Research question
<p>Theoretical: Engage with debates on the role of institutional regimes in shaping housing outcomes, by offering a better understanding of the role of the local scale in shaping specific housing outcomes.</p> <p>Practical: Underline the strategies and mechanisms that can be leveraged by localities to tackle specific problems, within the restrictions imposed by higher order institutional rules.</p>	<p>• To what extent can localities shape specific housing outcomes in large urban development projects in divergence from nationally steered policies and pressures from a Neoliberal economic system?</p>
Theoretical framework	Case studies
<p style="text-align: center;">Global economic context Post-keynesian Neoliberalism</p>	<p>Grenoble:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary case study • Different projects spanning multiple periods (2-3) <p>Other French city (TBD):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As a national comparison base <p>Secondments in Lisbon and Cyprus:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As primary international comparative ground

Life Cycle Economic and Social Cost-based Design

ESR4: Aya Eghandour

Supervisor: Professor Ebrahim Habibi
Co-supervisors: Dr. Ezzamel Hawatreh, Dr. Varun Munera Ravi
Host University: Sheffield University

Housing affordability & housing quality are two key facets that influence social housing problems. The first is concerned with the overall cost of having and maintaining a house without adding unwanted financial pressure which may lead to psychological burdens on households. While housing quality is pertinent to providing pleasant, healthy, durable, and safe indoor and outdoor built environment, which in return rises housing costs.

Research Aim

Support architects research socially informed decision-making?
Develop a market-friendly framework that integrates LCCA, occupants' real needs and feedback, and BIM in early design stages where the most influential building decisions are made.

Research Questions

- How prioritizing reducing LCC can influence social cost?
- Are occupants' lifestyles would impact LCC of a house?
- How social feedback can be integrated in BIM workflow?
- What challenges in this integration facing in reality?
- What suitable workflow for this integration will support architect?

Research Methodology

Adopting a mixed approach of quantitative and qualitative research methods.

Research Significance

Enabling informed economic and social-based housing design decision-making using BIM would. Promote housing sustainability and improve affordability.

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101019718.

Environmental Sustainability of Future social Housing

ESRS | Mahmoud Alawad

Supervisor: Prof. Karem-Edy,
Co-supervisors: Dr. Prayansh Nainani, Dr. Ignacio Galber,
Host University: Sheffield University

Comparative analysis of social housing policies' modernization impacts in selected post-socialist countries

ESRS: Marko Horvat

Supervisor: prof. dr. sc. Srećka Belizan
 Lead University: Institute for Social Policy, Faculty of Law, University of Zagreb, Croatia

Housing crises and its impact on adequate housing

ESR7: Anna Martin

Supervisor: Prof. Dr. Adrienne Cismady

Host Institution: Institute for Sociology, Centre for Social Sciences, Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Centre of Excellence

Aims

The purpose of this research is to investigate the origins of the housing crisis and its implications in Central and Eastern Europe and to understand the main causal mechanisms and conflicting paradigms that formulated the current situation.

Relevance

Unaffordable and inadequate housing leads to inequalities. These inequalities cause significant differences in lifetime earnings, reinforcing unwanted tendencies.

Phases of the research

Expected outcomes

- Identification of the causes of changing housing needs and intensified disparities
- Identification of best practices of adequate housing (e.g. co-operative action between local authorities, housing providers, social service providers), regeneration programmes and financial innovations
- Promotion of the importance of adequate housing

Urban Living Labs and the Role of Users in the Co-creation of Sustainable Housing: Housing as Community Infrastructure

ESRI: Andreas Panagidis

Supervisor: Dr Neel's Charalambous
Host University: University of Cyprus

From creator to enabler: exploring the potential of co-design, build courses in contemporary architectural education

ESR9: Effrosyni Rousou

Supervisor: Dr. Nedia Charalambous
Rust University, University of Cyprus

A set of strategies in creating and running a transdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder co-design build course that 'thinks globally but operates locally' as well as a thorough and reflexive evaluation of the experimentation process.

Retrofit of existing buildings and cohousing : Co-creation of sustainable living environments

ESRT- Zoi Tziika

Supervisor: Carli Nierman
 Host: Uniwersytet Politechniczny w Katowicach (UPK)

1. FRAMEWORK OF RESEARCH

1.1. Research objectives

- The research addresses demand for affordable ways of living, as a reaction to the existing crisis and its consequences on housing markets for the existing urban areas.
- Address objectives as identifying the economic, social, environmental and cultural factors that influence the development of housing and the development of sustainable living environments.
- Identify opportunities for collaboration, appropriate, self-management and empowerment of the residents and design policies that aim to include voluntary stakeholders.

1.2. Research questions

Can local communities retrofit the existing built environment through co-creation to create affordable, sustainable and collective ways of living?

2. MAKING THE SCENE

3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Can an affordable and sustainable living environment be created by existing urban buildings?
 Is it economically viable to retrofit existing urban buildings using financial and social capital?
 Can we create strong economic, social and cultural benefits from retrofitting?
 Can we create a strong social, economic and cultural benefits from retrofitting?
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 Can we create a strong social, economic and cultural benefits from retrofitting?

4. POINTS TO CONSIDER

- Can the existing urban buildings be retrofitted to the existing urban buildings?
- Can the existing urban buildings be retrofitted to the existing urban buildings?
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- Can the existing urban buildings be retrofitted to the existing urban buildings?

4. CONCLUSIONS

Can we create a strong social, economic and cultural benefits from retrofitting?
 Can we create a strong social, economic and cultural benefits from retrofitting?
 Can we create a strong social, economic and cultural benefits from retrofitting?
 Can we create a strong social, economic and cultural benefits from retrofitting?

5. METHODOLOGY

Comparative Analysis of Affordable and Sustainable Housing Policies in Europe

ESR12: Alex Fernandez

Supervisor: Marja Elsinga, Marietta Hafner and Gojko Bozovic

Host University: TU Delft

The main research goal is to identify and compare policies for the affordable retrofit of Europe's built environment. The analytical framework draws from various disciplines including economics, public policy, and complexity science. These disciplines provide the foundations to **four research streams**:

1. Analysing of **user costs and cash-flows** implications for various housing retrofit policies.
2. Formulating an **Agent-Based Model** of the housing market.
3. Adapting the preceding model to **comparatively** account for particularities across countries and urban areas.
4. Exploring **institutional and policy design** across different public and private organisations.

Output I: Identification and mapping of policy solutions

- From the European to regional and local levels
- According to different funding streams

Output II: A quantitative evaluation tool that measures policies

- Financial implications and stock retrofit
- Affordability across tenures and incomes

Output III: Policy recommendations tailored to different areas and actors

- Actionable research
- Transferable across different contexts

Citizen participation evaluation and urban co-governance: lessons from BIP/ZIP and the world of commons

ESR13: Androniki Pappa

Supervisor: Alexandra Melo
 Host University: ISCTE - Instituto Universitário de Lisboa

Social Evaluation of Regeneration

Housing regeneration in Europe: Possibilities for social value creation in the context of the Renovation Wave

ESR15: Leonardo Ricaurte
 Supervisor: Fibra Samuel
 Host University: University of Reading

Annex 3 – Networking session

Red group

Carla Sentieri (Supervisor)

Effrosyni Roussou (ESR9)

Leonadro Ricaurte (ESR14)

Green group

Karim Hadjri (Supervisor)

Saskia Furman (ESR2)

Alex Fernández (ESR12)

Yellow group

Paulette Duarte (co-supervisor)

Christophe Verrier (ESR3)

Zoe Tzika (ESR10)

Orange group

Krzysztof Nawratek (co-supervisor)

Mahmoud Alsaeed (ESR5)

Andreas Panagidis (ESR8)

Purple group

Vasco Moreira Rato (co-supervisor)

Aya Elghandour (ESR4)

Tijn Croon (ESR11)

Annex 4 – Event evaluation form

RE-DWELL Lisbon Workshop– Quality assessment

22-24 September 2021

This evaluation is to be completed by all participants, ESRs as well as supervisors, co-supervisors, secondment representatives.

Your answers will help to improve the next network activities. Thanks for your cooperation!

* Required

1. Please select your profile*

- a) ESR
- b) Supervisor
- c) Co-supervisor
- d) Secondment

2. How did you attend? *

- a) Online
- b) Onsite
- c) Both

3. How would you rate the organization of the workshop? (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)*

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

4. How would you evaluate the online sessions? (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)*

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

5. Please evaluate ESRs' Research Projects session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1

- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

- Briefly explain the reasons for your ESRs Research Projects session evaluation

6. Please evaluate Lisbon Municipality session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

- Briefly explain the reasons for your ESRs Research Projects session evaluation

7. Please evaluate Roundtable session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

- Briefly explain the reasons for your ESRs Research Projects session evaluation

8. Please evaluate CASAIS session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

- Briefly explain the reasons for your ESRs Research Projects session evaluation

9. Please evaluate Transferrable Skills session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4

e) 5

- Briefly explain the reasons for your ESRs Research Projects session evaluation

10. Please evaluate ISCTE session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

a) 1

b) 2

c) 3

d) 4

e) 5

- Briefly explain the reasons for your ESRs Research Projects session evaluation

11. Any other comments or suggestions for upcoming network activities (workshops, summer schools)*

Open answer